

LF mentorship session Tools and Techniques to Debug an Embedded Linux System

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- To debug a problem follow the steps:
 - o Understand the problem
 - o Reproduce the problem
 - o Identify the root cause
 - o Apply the fix
 - o Test it, if good celebrate if bad go back to step one
- 5 types of problems:
 - o Crashes
 - o Lockup/ hang
 - o Logic/implementation
 - o Resource leakage, memory leakage is the most common.
 - o (lack of) performance
- Tools and techniques to debug:
 - o Our brains
 - o Post mortem analysis (logging analysis, memory dump analysis) which means the debugging happens after the problem, by using information generated by the system.
 - o Tracing / profiling (specialized logging): it is a specialized type of logging and it can be used for debugging and for performance analysis.
 - o Interactive debugging (e.g. GDB)
 - o Debugging frameworks (e.g. Valgrind)
- Use the tool "ulimit" to know the size of the problem, when you are doing post mortem analysis.
- Some tools for tracing is "kernel shark" or using "ftrace". Trace debugging is the type most similar to print statement in python
- Interactive debugging is a way to debug during runtime, by setting break points and